

Investigating the change of the organizational communication in the government system of Afghanistan after the fall of Taliban

Researcher: Professor Mohammad Dawod Nabeel

Abstract

Since the beginning of their formation, human societies have sought to create structures to organize their lives. And they experienced many methods to establish a good relationship between government institutions and citizens. Therefore, we can say that since the beginning of creation, humans have made a lot of efforts to satisfy their needs and transmit their messages and thoughts, and for this reason, they have tested various experiences. Therefore, communication has had a profound impact on their lives.

Talking about administration and how it communicates in group life, especially in society, makes sense when the process and structure of life is based on the system of citizenship and good governance. In this article, I will try to analyze a part of this process, which is organizational communication, and make it clear the process of the formation of organizational communication system in the Afghanistan after the fall of the first round of Taliban in 2001 and the establishment of the Bonn Summit. and which path has it taken and has it responded to the needs of our society during this period? or not.

Keywords: Taliban, Afghanistan, organizational communication, government, Bonn Summit.

Introduction

The discussion of the evolution of organizational communication is actually a discussion of changing the shape of communication methods that were simple in the past and now with the advancement of science, industry and technology, it has taken on a new face that is completely different from the previous methods.

Knowing the evolution process of organizational communication helps people to understand the conditions and choose the media they need according to the requirements of the time. and communicate with others in the easiest way. For example: today, as a member of the global village, we cannot communicate with the other party using basic communication methods; Because these methods are currently not usable and do not answer the needs of contemporary human communication. We need to reach out to new media and take advantage of them. To be able to communicate effectively.

And on the other hand, we can make maximum use of communication media such as: radio, television, internet, cable, etc. in the way of growth and improvement of human culture and knowledge in our society and make our society Let us introduce to the world that this kind of thing could not be touched in the first period of the Taliban regime, and the country was far away from such issues that we mentioned above, and before the Taliban, the Mujahideen Islamic Government in Afghanistan did not have much modern and efficient organizational structures and communications. The use of new technology was not used in the structure of the country's administration. And the Taliban, by conquering Kabul and creating a regime called the Emirate, did not make any effort to create a systematic structure with contemporary technology in the country and even removed modern and modern symbols, for example: At that time, I was young, according to the need. I went to the headquarters of the Grand Chancellery Palace, the Taliban had even thrown away the desk and chair and were sitting on the carpet that was flat on the ground and were taking care of the affairs of technology and computers, and there was no mention of these issues.

Today's world is the world of communication. Professional knowledge, accurate information and commitment to the organization's goals are considered the biggest capital of the organization's leadership, and it is based on this capital that public relations create and grow two-way, useful

and professional communication for the benefit of the organization. Organizational communication should rely on thinking, participation, innovation, initiative and response to public opinion. The knowledge and resources of public relations are mentioned as the most civil part of the organization, to facilitate communication and create mutual trust between the government and the people. Public relations should have a special place in every organizations, and besides that, engineers, specialists, doctors, clerics, soldiers, teachers, etc. can share their voice with the audience in the best way through the public relations channel of their organization, otherwise the work of Out of the hands of professionals, it causes misunderstandings (Cheney, George. (2007). Organizational communication.)

It should be noted that public relations puts the media at the service of their organization and conveys the voice of the organization to thousands of audiences at the same time. This itself causes the circulation of correct information and creates a credible face for the organization, this ability can only be found in the potential of public relations professionals. They create a two-way, authentic and sustainable interaction for organizations that will satisfy everyone.

Research Goal

In general, the goals of this research are as follows:

- a) How did the transformation process of organizational communication in Afghanistan begin?
- b) Evaluating the transformation of organizational communication and examining the issue under which factors these forms were transformed and which consequences did this transformation have for the country?
- c) By understanding the consequences of this process, determining the future path of development in the country.
- d) Creating knowledge is a phenomenon of organizational communication and the whole concept of communication.

The Importance Of Research

Technology and its application in the field of social, political and economic systems and structures is of great importance, and due to its importance, the discussion of electronic

government and good governance is being discussed today. Managing the country is nothing else and this is where democracy makes sense.

According to Marshall McLuhan¹, a Canadian scientist: Internet and media, which are actually means of communication, have turned the world into a small village today and provided opportunities to create electronic government, as if we were to understand the nature and function of Internet and media today. If we are not aware of public and individual issues, we cannot keep up with other societies that use this; They know the tools, let's use them to build the economic, political, social and cultural infrastructures of our society, if we as a nation want to achieve progress. I have to make maximum use of these tools so that we can lead our society to progress and fulfill my responsibility, which can only be realized through full knowledge of these tools.

Research Hypothesis

It is believed that after the establishment of the temporary administration, the transformation of organizational communication took place in Afghanistan.

The Main Research Question:

First Question:

Which factors played a greater role in the transformation of organizational communication in post-Taliban Afghanistan?

Research Sub-Questions:

First question:

Which channel has played the most role in the formation of organizational communication?

The second question:

How much has the role of awareness and the emergence of a new political atmosphere played in the evolution of organizational communication in Afghanistan?

The third question:

Is the distance between the government and the people the result of the lack of communication between the government and the people, or the distrust of the people towards the government?

¹ Marshal McLuhan, 1911 - 1980

Research Methods

In this research, I have used analytical and descriptive research methods. And I tried to refer to, many reliable scientific sources.

Background Research

Unfortunately, no research has been done on the evolution of organizational communication after the fall of the first term of the Taliban in 2001, and the holding of the Bonn Summit in Afghanistan, although there are some writings about the Taliban and their actions in Dari and English, which are not enough. And this is perhaps the first research on this matter, so we can say that this is a pure new research in this case.

Theoretical Foundations Of Research

History Of Administration And Management Of The Organization

The history of administration and management begins in some ways from the very beginning of mankind, so that primitive humans were forced to cooperate with their fellow humans and ask them to cooperate in order to meet their basic needs such as food, clothing, shelter and other necessities. In this way, the issue of division of labor was raised for the first time. From the time of the caliphate of Adam and his children, we see clear examples of a type of administration and management. In the same way, in ancient civilizations, there have been advances in the fields of agriculture, urban development, making laws, the growth of art and literature, and the like, all of which are impressive and representative of the existence of order and division of work and administration related to the same era. (Mohmand, Administration and Management, 9:

In the 9th to 11th centuries AD, various sciences, especially wisdom and philosophy, flourished and the qualities of a leader were mentioned by Farabi². He considers the qualities of a good leader to be intelligence, memory, administration, power of expression and thinking. Ghazali³ in his book (Nasiha al-Muluk) has declared qualities such as: justice, intelligence, patience and servitude as special for leaders and they should be avoided. He advised against jealousy, anger, narrow-mindedness and self-righteousness (Mohamand, Administration and Management, 10:

The emergence of concepts such as good governance indicates the changing role of governments in managing societies and changing attitudes towards the functioning of government in today's world. Currently, even in market-based economies, governments are expected to perform several major tasks well, such as: maintaining macroeconomic stability, providing public goods and services, developing economic and technical infrastructure, preventing market stagnation, developing Equality and social justice and control of administrative and economic corruption.

If we add the protection of human rights, the sustainable development of human resources and the environment to this list, we will definitely move in line with the global wave of enriching the duties of the government. According to what was mentioned under the title of good governance, one can feel the difficulty of managing the development needed today. If in the past development

² Abu Nasr Al-Farabi

³ Abu Hamid Al-Ghazali

meant a limited high economic growth rate, today complex qualitative variables have been used as criteria for evaluating the performance of governments on the path of development. For example: United Nations Human Rights Commission, factors such as democracy, freedom of expression and participation, equality, environmental management and environmental protection, protection of human rights, law-oriented, providing optimal services to people, transparency and accountability, security , peace, conflict management, raising the level of citizens' awareness and electronic government have been introduced as evaluation criteria for governments. On the one hand, it seems that the realization of a good governance depends to some extent on the degree of realization of this at the international level. , the transparency of financial processes, the health of the world's monetary system and the degree of health of international organizations in the political and judicial sphere can have significant effects on the process of realizing good governance in the countries of the world. With these considerations, some actions that can put societies on the path of good governance are mentioned.

Clearer definition of duties and missions of government institutions in order to avoid parallel work and reduce costs.

Creating transparency through respect for freedom of expression and the principle of access to information and media.

Making the current structure of government organizations simpler and more reasonable, Reforming local institutions (local governments) and redefining their relations with central organizations in the direction of decentralization.

Reducing paperwork and seriously fighting all kinds of corruption such as: administrative, political, social and cultural.

Improving the quality of public and private sector services.

Amendment of laws and regulations and salary system in the private sector.

Realization of electronic government through the use of information technology in government agencies.

Reforming management systems, especially paying attention to competence in the selection, appointment and promotion of government officials.

Reforming the budgeting system and the tax system is focusing on the results of economic development policies in line with the sustainable development of human resources, the expansion of social justice and the activation of economic capacities and the optimal use of available resources. (Prabakaran, Madhu, What is Good Governance?, Available in SSRN)

What Is Communication?

As we said above, the word "communication" is derived from the Latin root "communis" which means sharing. This word is used in the Persian language in the form of the Arabic infinitive Bab Aftaal, which in the word means to connect, to relate, and in the form of an infinitive noun, it is used in the meaning of connection, connection, connection and relationship.

Communication researchers make a difference between the singular meaning of communication and the plural meaning of communication (Amid, Hassan, 1389: 19).

In 1909 Cooley⁴, in his famous book called Social Organization, while pointing out the important role of new forms of communication in creating justice and international brotherhood, Cooley⁴ defined communication as follows: Communication is a mechanism based on and through which human relations exist. comes and all the intellectual manifestations of means of transmission and preservation in space and time are developed based on it. The communication of facial expressions, behaviors, echoes of voice, movements, words, writings, printing, railway, telegraph, telephone and all the devices that have been made recently in order to overcome space and time, includes them all (Motamed Nejad, 1386:27).

In fact, element of progress and development of communities is considered the key emancipation of nations from domination and dependence, As well as the development of foundations of society is a tool for strengthening of constant peace and stability, which nations are always in need of it. (Nabeel, Mohammad Dawod, (July 1, 2022), Investigating the Position of Independent Media in Afghanistan from the Interim Administration to the National Unity Government.)

From the above sentences, we conclude that communication is fundamental and universal. The main basis of public relations work is the communication process. The simplest form of

⁴ Charles Cooley, 1864 - 1929

communication is the transfer of information from one person to another, or more seriously to a device that produces and stores news (Fanous, Miraziz Ahmad, 13:1390).

In a more precise sense: communication is a special kind of social behavior or mutual behavior, during which the intended concept is directly transferred to the receiver with the help of signs specific to the subject (Dadegaran, Seyyed Mohammad, 1388: 15).

- "Emery⁵" defines the concept of communication in a general sense (with special attention to social communication) as follows: "Communication is the technique of transferring information and human thoughts and behaviors from one person to another. In general, every person He uses various means to establish a relationship with others and convey his messages to them. For example: when a person says "good morning" to another person, he understands his friendship and intimacy by verbal expression. So, when a person writes a letter to another person, he expresses his intention in writing and establishes a relationship with him (Saroukhani Baqir, 2004: 31).

In my opinion, communication is the process of transmitting a message from its source to its recipient, while communication means studying the technical tools and equipment of this phenomenon. This process is sometimes referred to as a manager's responsibility (employee relations). In the management of matters such as human communication, factors affecting communication, informal and formal groups, ways to improve communication in removing communication barriers and considering human relations in the organization are important, employee communication is a continuous process and requires skill in sending and Receive the message.

Knowing about the communication process and its application in the organization and using appropriate methods of message transmission in the organization helps managers in guiding the organization and employees and causes the development of the organization.

Employee communication has many characteristics and limitations, but it is delicate and complex, and for this reason, it must be carefully managed.

⁵ Edwin Emery

Organizational Communication Or Public Relations

Underestimating the importance of strong organizational communication is a mistake that from time to time puts heavy costs on the shoulders of organizations, which was well observed in the Mujahideen administration and after Taliban.

In fact, organizational communication or public relations is a set of techniques that are used in a cost-effective, cheap and mostly free manner; It is for the purpose of providing trust between the organization and society, between the organization and its beneficiaries, and finally between the organization and everyone. The only thing that public relations need is the unconditional support of the organization's leadership, that's when public relations agents use all their skills to gain trust and create popularity for the leadership of their department and institution, and small and large media, modern and traditional, Social and non-social, printed and electronic, they put everyone in the service of their organization in a magical and unbelievable way (Kapur, Radhika. (2018). Organizational Communication).

The foundation of organizational communication is formed by the artistic nature of this field, therefore it is easy, cheap, audience-oriented, solution-oriented and legal.

The fundamental goal of public relations is to expand human relations inside and outside the organization in order to correctly obtain the support of each person the organization deals with.

Public Relations In The Cultural Context Of Afghanistan

Public relations is a new term that refers to the government literature department of Afghanistan, which is generally responsible for providing communications and correspondence. But this term is still used in its traditional sense in Afghan government organizations, and there is a very weak perception in this matter. That is, it mostly refers to an institution that is responsible for publishing and broadcasting, while public relations, which is more than a century old, is a product of a modern administrative and organizational structure that revolves around interaction, exchange and two-way communication.

Contrary to the unknown nature of public relations in Afghanistan, this concept and profession is not a new phenomenon in the world. Public relations, which is more than a century old, has now been promoted to an important applied knowledge and a prestigious academic discipline and is an integral part of organizations and offices. The social democratic and people-oriented function

of today's organizations and administrations has made the existence, position and role of public relations undeniable.

Without effective and dynamic public relations, the life and development of organizations cannot be imagined. Public relations, in the role of an honest and impartial intermediary, conveys the goals, programs, services and products of organizations and companies to their audiences and, in return, conveys the wishes, needs, opinions and suggestions of customers and audiences to organizations and companies (Nabeel, Mohammad Dawod, Strengths and Weaknesses of the Ministry of Information and Culture of Afghanistan in Managing Private T.V Stations (From 2010 to 2020) (October 20, 2021)).

In general, the responsibility of public relations is the management of internal and external human relations. Managers and brokers, experts and professionals of public relations, by applying management methods and principles, seek to organize and dynamize internal organizational factors, and by using strategies and new communication tools and mass communication tools, they seek to inform, find information, advertise, encourage, promote and management of public opinion. Basically, all these approaches and role-playing serve the success, competition and development of organizations and offices, and it is realized when public relations simultaneously protect the interests of the organization and the customer (Nabeel, Mohammad Dawod, Investigating Journalists' Lack of Access to Information From Afghan Government Agencies (October 7, 2021)).

Despite the importance and necessity of public relations in organizations and offices, before the Taliban regime in Afghanistan, it must be said: the Taliban did not believe in it at all, and after the Taliban in the past twenty years, this profession in Afghanistan has remained at the level of "public relations" of the traditional bureaucracy and has had an impressive impact. There is no constructive interaction between the administration and the clients.

One of the main reasons for people's dissatisfaction and the creation of a gap between the government and the nation in both public and private administrations is the absence of modern public relations in their organizational structure. For example, according to the usual procedure, the officials of the government offices would get information about the challenges and problems

of the administration under their management from the media, and they would also give what they want to the media through announcements and press conferences.

The biggest challenge of government organizations in the last twenty years in Afghanistan has been their lack of work in the correct and transparent implementation of their responsibilities towards the citizens. In the absence of effective and dynamic public relations, it was always difficult for government departments to serve citizens, and people wandered for weeks and months to sign a letter. In the end, this problem had caused the unemployment of the administration and the rise of administrative corruption. Most of the administrative corruption in Afghanistan has been due to bureaucracy, paperwork, and unnecessary bureaucracy, which draws citizens to brokers and administrative shareholders.

This problem was not only affecting most of the government offices of Afghanistan, but foreign organizations and donor countries in Afghanistan also had the same problem. While the reality of Afghanistan was something else and there was less voting with people, professors, women and civil society, and this was a serious problem. The key to solving this problem lies in the hands of professional public relations units that protect the interests of the administration or organization and its applicants and audiences. An expert and professional public relations manager can review his organization and office every six months and find out its strengths and weaknesses. Instead of justifying the weaknesses, plan a long-term plan and solution and turn the strengths of the organization into a source of inspiration and credibility of the organization to its customers and audiences. That did not happen.

Communications After The Bonn Summit

The Taliban were a political and religious group, although according to Atai, their knowledge did not exceed the scope of a few limited religious books, but they were able to make room for themselves in most of the provinces of the country (Atai, *Modern History of Afghanistan*, 565: 565).

The worldview of this group was limited and narrow. All in all, this group did not believe in the magnificence of running the government and their society, nor did they let others do the work, in fact, during the first period of the Taliban regime, it cannot be called a regular communication system, there was no military at all, in fact it was a regime. Based on tribal beliefs and their

actions were based on tribal values, for example: all orders were issued by one person, whether it was good or bad, and then it was implemented, and their administrative relationship was at a very low level. A tribal relationship such as: the use of letters and papers by a specific person, in fact such a relationship in the 21st century, which the whole world calls this century the "information revolution" century, is neither acceptable nor rational. (Attai, Modern History of Afghanistan, p. 565.)

In the first period of the Taliban regime, the gates of science and knowledge were still closed to everyone, the economic problems of the nation had spread, people needed bread more than anything, people's attention was only limited to how many days they could survive, the sense of work and Technology had been erased from the public mind, the state of society was in a state of stagnation, especially the state of telecommunications and information technology.

According to the statistics of The Ministry of Communications and Information Technology, before 2001, only one person in every 450 person had access to telephone services. This shows the extreme backwardness of a society, Afghans not only had no communication with the outside world, but were also unable to provide communication with each other, the state of communication and telecommunications at that time was a telling picture of the realities of Afghanistan's society at that time, that is, dark and isolated Afghanistan.

Temporary Government

Following the fall of the Taliban, a meeting was held in Bonn, Germany at the initiative of the United Nations in order to form a government to replace the Taliban. This meeting was chaired by Lakhdar Brahimi, the representative of the United Nations in Afghanistan affairs, and various countries and groups participated in it. The Bonn meeting lasted for 20 days and led to an agreement based on which the interim government headed by Hamid Karzai was formed for six months, Karzai became the head of the Afghan government and hopes were created that Afghanistan would progress. It felt like something big had happened. It was believed that the only person who can gather all the groups and parties in this country is Hamid Karzai, who happened to be welcomed by the people of this country. Karzai's success in the first term of the presidency of Afghanistan was almost predictable. Because in a short time, he was able to agree with foreign countries as well as internal groups. (The unsaid of the Bonn conference, 17th of October 2016, 8 Sobh newspaper. Interview with Mohammad Natghi).

Finally, the temporary administration of Hamid Karzai, composed of five deputy ministers and 23 ministers, took over power from Burhanuddin Rabbani in 1980. This office, which was the result of 9 days of negotiations and discussions between the conflicting parties in the Afghanistan issue, was formed for six months and was tasked with preparing the preparations for the emergency Loya Jirga. The first commission was in charge of forming the Loya Jirga, the second commission was in charge of preparing and drafting the new constitution of Afghanistan to present to the Loya Jirga, and the third commission was in charge of investigating the issue of immigrants and regulating issues related to human rights (Amirzadeh, Haroon: 182-183).

The government or the temporary government can be called an all-controversial government and all-out conflict over power, and for this reason, the temporary period did not make any changes in relation to the economic, social, technology, and administrative structure.

Transitional Period

In the transition period, the structure of the administration was slowly put in order. Anyway, after the Taliban, the growth of communication and telecommunication technology in Afghanistan has been really amazing and has had a tremendous impact on the evolution of the country's social, political and economic life. The level of investment in the field of communication has increased from zero in 1380 to two billion dollars in 1395. While during the Taliban era, only 15,000 telephone lines were active only in big cities and less than 1% of people had access to telephone services. Because when schools, mass communication devices, radio, television and press and scientific and technical institutions are blocked on a society, how can we talk about communication and relationships.

A large number of girls were sent to schools from the temporary and transitional administration to the Karzai presidency, and their number has never been so large, new universities have been established or revived, and many radio and television transmitters are the most prosperous media sector in created the region (DW 05. 04. 2014).

Presidential Election

At the end of the 18th, the balance of power was in favor of the people, and this time Hamid Karzai was officially announced as the first president of Afghanistan after the end of the counting of votes. After that, the United Nations fact-finding commission in its detailed report

announced that the shortcomings of the elections were partial and had no effect on the overall process and its results, and pointed out some of the existing defects and problems to Karzai's rivals (Iqtidar Melli Weekly, No. 93, October 16, 2008).

In spite of all these irregularities, disorders and injustices, the government of Hamid Karzai was able to develop better and better in the field of technology, which we witnessed an incredible development in Karzai's government. More than 22 million people had access to telecommunication services and telecommunication networks covered more than 70% of the country's land in 34 provinces. While internet services did not exist during the Taliban era, today more than 5 million of our compatriots are connected to each other and the world through internet networks. And they can solve their problems well, communicate with the whole world, their level of awareness will increase. Again, because such a thing was new in Afghanistan, people complained about its high price, after going through almost a year. The 3G internet service launched in 2011 has been extended to all 34 provinces of the country since the decade of Karzai's administration. In 2013, fortunately, Afghanistan was able to launch its first satellite into space. The creation of more than 4,000 kilometers of optical fiber lines has transformed the internet service infrastructure and made it accessible to everyone. Today, Afghanistan's optical fiber network is connected to the countries of Pakistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Iran. On the other hand, the expansion of telecommunication services has provided new sources of revenue for the Afghan government. Today, 200 million dollars, which is 12 percent of the government's total revenue, is financed through the tax on telecommunications and communication networks. The Afghan government earns more than 50 million dollars annually from the fiber optic network tax alone. More than 120,000 of our compatriots are still provided with the opportunity to work in the telecommunication and communication sector, and it is expected that the number will increase in the future. In the last twenty years, Afghanistan has changed from the most backward country in terms of telecommunications and communication services to the most advanced country in this field in the region.

But again, despite all these advances and advancements in the technology sector during the thirteen-year rule of Hamid Karzai, government departments could not use technology in its proper form (new technology in providing good governance and a dynamic society. <http://afghanistanembassy.org.uk/dari/Pashto/wp-content>).

National Unity Government

Fortunately, the national unity government, realizing the importance of new technology in improving the administration and management of the country, took important initiatives in line with its implementation in government offices. In order to provide greater coordination and work efficiency between government departments, for the first time, a new system for accepting applications and reviewing them called Presidential Docs was created in the Office of the President of Afghanistan. In this system, all applications and requests are automatically coded and received and checked without wasting time.

The introduction of this system reduced the receipt of complaints from days and weeks to 48 hours. At the same time, the presidential office has been equipped with a video conference communication system to ensure communication between the presidential office and ministries, governors, and other high-ranking government officials. At the same time, a special digital system has been designed to follow the affairs, to implement the president's decisions and orders. The Ministry of Finance has also implemented the electronic governance system for customs supervision, recruitment management and planning in the relevant institutions of that ministry. In addition, to provide transparency and prevent administrative corruption, the Ministry of Finance launched the e-pay system, according to which national businessmen and investors can pay their taxes without problems in all banks of the country. The implementation of electronic governance systems has been effective in reducing corruption and providing transparency on the one hand, and on the other hand, it has also increased government revenue, as the government's revenue in 2014 shows a 21% increase.

In the Ministry of Interior, since 2013, 97 percent of the country's police force registers in the biometric system and receives their salaries electronically. The registration of police personnel in this system enabled the government to have sufficient information about the number of people and the capacities of the country's police force. In general, it can be said that more than 73 percent of the 800,000 government employees receive their salaries electronically. Paying the salaries of government officials has been effective in reducing corruption and the loss of government revenue.

The distribution of identity cards in electronic form, as well as electronic passports and taking exams for the appointment of government officials in electronic form, are major issues that can be mentioned as examples.

Today, the new technology of communication and telecommunications has transformed the governance system in Afghanistan in an unprecedented way. The National Unity Government of Afghanistan tried to make the process of governance easier by using communication technology effectively and to fight corruption on the other hand.

With the increasing development of communication technology in the country, we can boldly say: the age of isolation and darkness in Afghanistan has ended, although administrative corruption did not disappear until the end and continued in Afghan offices until the Taliban regime came to power again, and in fact one of the reasons for the fall of the republican system and the failure of the international community in Afghanistan was the existence of administrative corruption (new technology in providing good governance and a dynamic society. <http://afghanistanembassy.org.uk/dari/Pashto>).

Research Results

1: Which factors have played a greater role in the evolution of organizational communication after the Taliban in Afghanistan?

- a) Appropriate conditions: 20.27%
- b) Organizational planning: 8.42%
- c) Security: 42.16%
- d) Global aid: 29.15%

2: Which channels are used more to provide better public relations?

- a) Media: 26.15%
- b) Email: 45.29%
- c) Fax: 3.42%
- d) Traditional correspondence: 25.14%

3: How much role did people's awareness and needs, play in the evolution of Afghanistan's organizational communication?

- a) High 25.15%
- b) Very high 42.16%
- c) Moderate 8.42%
- d) Low 24.27%

e) It had no role 0%

4: Is the distance between the government and the people caused by lack of good communication, or by people's distrust of the government?

- a) lack of good communication 46.64%
- b) people's disbelief towards the government 53.36%

5 : How do you evaluate the effectiveness of public relations agencies of government institutions?

- a) Good 27.15%
- b) Very Good 35.45%
- c) Average 8%
- d) Worrying 29.4%

Qualitative Results

In about 80 percent of the interviews planned in relation to this issue, it is concluded that the process of organizational communication in Afghanistan has progressed well, and most of those I interviewed stated that the evolution of organizational communication in Afghanistan before its fall again in August 2021 It has really progressed unprecedentedly, although it does not have a good proportion to the amount of aid from the international community and the emergence of suitable conditions, but it is still not possible to ignore the progress in this sector.

Conclusion

As a result of this research, it can be said that the existence of security has provided 42.16% of the country's growth, and in the second stage, the assistance of the international community has contributed 29.15% to the transformation of the country's organizational communication, which has caused organizational transformation in Afghanistan over the years. has passed, and the existence of appropriate programs from government agencies contributed 8.42 percent.

The results of this question show that although the right conditions were prepared and there was general security, while the aid of the international community continued to flow generously, government organizations still suffer from the lack of detailed plans, most of the plans are from foreign donors and Provincial reconstruction teams and similar institutions were suggested and implemented. For example: the Justice Department of the Supreme Court from Italy, the Ministry of Education from UNESCO and Canada and other institutions and the Ministry of Higher Education from the World Bank, the Ministry of Interior from Germany, the Civil Service Reforms Commission from England, Supreme Audit Office by PKF organization, financing and equipping and its employees were educated and trained. It can be said that the evolution of Afghanistan's organizational communication in this period was owed to the security and assistance of the international community rather than organizational planning in the government departments of Afghanistan, but during the time of the national unity government and after that, the government organizations became somewhat program-oriented and good plans presented. Regarding which channels were used more to provide better public relations, it should be said that in this part of the referendum, 100 people participated, it shows that the use of modern communication channels is growing rapidly in the country and the majority of communication channels with People and people with government institutions especially in Afghanistan are in the process of modernization. The figure: 45.29% shows that the use of e-mail has grown well in the process of communication and administrative correspondence, and the use of the media channel in the country as a better means of information is encouraging to the extent of 26.15%. But the use of traditional ducts with a quantity of 25.14 percent is still considered as a big challenge.

It should also be said that people's awareness and need for the development of the country has also played a good role in the transformation of Afghanistan's organizational communication. If

we take a look at the following options: A: High 25.15% B: Very high 42.16% C: Medium 8.42% D: Low 24.27%, it can be seen that most of the Afghan citizens left the country after the end of the war in the country. Far and near returned to Afghanistan and played a role in the transformation process of the country based on the need and necessity of the people to develop their social, political and economic life and put pressure on the government to achieve development. Because the returnees brought their knowledge, skills, and life experience from abroad to the country, and the people who were inside the country have also significantly increased their political knowledge by following the media information from moment to moment. Therefore, these two reasons were considered a good opportunity for transformation in the country's administrative apparatus and organizations. And he urged the government to make efforts in the development of the country. And as for whether the distance between the government and the people is due to the lack of good communication, or the people's disbelief towards the government?

The results of the research show that the lack of good communication shows 46.64% and the people's disbelief towards the government shows 53.36%. In addition to these findings, it should be said that at the beginning of the first term of Karzai's government, the relationship between the people and the government was relatively good and the people voted for Karzai with the trust they had and it can be said that we had relatively good elections, but later the distance between the people and the government increased and due to fraud in the second election after the Taliban which was held in 2008, at first the amount Hamid Karzai's votes were announced at about 55 percent of the qualified votes, but after investigating fraud in the elections, Karzai's votes fell below 50 percent and the election was delayed to the second round. Abdullah Abdullah, Karzai's opponent, announced that in protest against the improper performance of the government and the commission He will not participate in the election and as a result, Karzai was declared the president-elect (Afghanistan presidential election (2008)-Wikipedia).

The fraudulent results of the presidential elections in Afghanistan became a reason for the people's distrust towards democracy, and the lack of adherence to the implementation of promised programs, the existence of corruption and insecurity, etc. became the reason for the people's distrust towards the government The elections of 2014 and the creation of a national

unity government increased with the initiative and mediation of US Secretary of State John Kerry (Mandigar newspaper, 6 September 2017).

Finally, the fraud in the fourth presidential election of 2019 and the failure of the efforts of US Special Representative Zalmay Khalilzad and US Secretary of State Mike Pompeo to solve this crisis, these optimisms all turned into disappointment (Islamic Republic News Agency, Afghanistan Presidential Election 2013, September 2019).

The political events of the country destroyed the people's belief in the republic and democracy, but the existence of some programs by the national unity government, especially in the field of telecommunications, technology and communication, caused the development of the country and changed the lives of the people. The level of corruption decreased slightly and increased with the collection of revenues with the implementation of the technical system in the Ministry of Finance. But putting pressure on the media and not providing proper information to the people by the government organizations led to the distance of these distances once again, for example: in the second term of Ghani's rule in 2021, for the first time, the media control department was appointed by Shivay Sharq, a certain publication in The Ministry of Information and Culture and Confirmation of the President of Afghanistan was created and this was an example to control the media.

Regarding the effectiveness of public relations agencies of government institutions, it should be said that option A: good shows 27.15%, and option B: better shows 35.45%, and option C: average shows 8%, and it is important that option D: It shows a worrying 29.4%. It must be said that after the fall of the first round of the Taliban regime, almost all the structures were broken and the new government established new structures and next to them, government public relations organizations. also established the foundation, which was a good and proper move, but in terms of giving importance to these organizations, the government was in trouble, and the installation of uneducated and inexperienced people on the basis of ethnic and linguistic relations caused these organizations to don't shine so brightly. And it was usually seen as an unemployed institution, and their entire activity was reduced to providing one-sided reports prepared by government organizations to the people. There was no big and modern vision in relation to public relations institutions at the government level, and there were considerations of taste in this field, for example: after 2014, when the Faculty of Journalism was established in Al-Biruni

University with the help of Dr. Barnayar and a group of students of this faculty. At that time, I was the head of this faculty, and I prepared a plan that, in the first stage, provided the opportunity to change the name of the faculty, and in the second stage, to modify and modernize its structure, based on compliance with the administrative hierarchy of this plan. The faculty and academic council of the university approved and the purpose of the next actions was sent to the Ministry of Higher Education. This plan, which was prepared based on the example of five universities in the region and the world, was not approved by the Ministry of Higher Education. The summary of the plan was that the name of the faculty was changed from the Faculty of Journalism within the first two departments of Radio and Television and the second Press to the Faculty of Communication and Media Sciences within the two departments, the Department of Media and the Department of Communications, while maintaining its organizational structure which is definitely It can be said that its effectiveness would have been much higher and it was the demand of the age and time. Unfortunately, this plan was rejected, and this issue made me and my colleagues wonder why a reputable government institution resists the introduction of sound reforms and makes mistakes like This is just a small example, continues the former. And this itself was a big scientific obstacle to create a public relations system in the public and private organizations of Afghanistan.

Therefore, Afghanistan's professional public relations have a good life of nearly 20 years, but the situation is such that there is no significant infrastructure for professional public relations in the country's large organizations, and public relations work individually and separately from the organizations. Public relations in Afghanistan are mostly known under the name of "press" or "publications" department, and they are deprived of having a professional and updated name that enjoys the direct support of the organization within the framework of the facilities and the governing laws. Press people are dependent on the top of the organization in an unprofessional way; Not dependent on the strategic goals of the organization, this is a narrow and difficult border that only professional eyes distinguish and worry about. Publications or the press department of national organizations do not benefit from today's infrastructure, technologies and facilities. They have little privileges and their work is reduced to a camera, a computer connected to the Internet, and a listening and obedient ear. Since most of the institutions of the country are technical and their work is managed by specific people with specific education, the view of the leadership of the organizations towards the press department is actually a top-down view, they

use them only for the purpose of "propaganda" and in high-level meetings. There is no place for this team, although with the scale of the situation and the influx of financial resources, excellent work has not been done and despite reformist thoughts and ideas to improve public relations, fundamental practical steps have not been taken in this field. But it can also be said that good things were done, especially in the years after Karzai. Therefore, the leadership of Afghan organizations should separate the border between advertising and public relations, provide comprehensive support to their professional public relations department, and accept them as active members in decision-making meetings. It is with all-round support that the public relations department of organizations can expand the organizational culture, transfer the capacities of the organization to the society and the views of the society to the leadership of the organization and reduce the fatal disconnection between the society and the organization.

Reference list

- 1) Afghanistan is the first legitimate leader". Iqtidar Melli Weekly, No. 93, 6 November 2004.
- 2) Amirzadeh, Haroun. ("Afghanistan: Political System Discussion and the Challenge of Federalism". Constitutional Law Conference, Mithaq Melli. <http://www.tolonews.tv/>.
- 3) Attai, Mohammad Ibrahim. 2003, Modern History of Afghanistan. Peshawar, Meyvand Publications. Number of pages 568)
- 4) Cheney, G. (2007). Organizational Communication Comes Out. Management Communication Quarterly, 21(1), 80–91. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0893318907302639>
- 5) Dadegaran, Seyyed Mohammad. 2008, the basics of social communication. Tehran: Firouze Publications, first edition.
- 6) Fanous, Miraziz Ahmad. 2010, Individual Conceptual Communications, Kabul: Azam Publications.
- 7) Kapur, Radhika. Organizational Communication. 2018, available at ResearchGate ([PDF](#)) [Organizational Communication \(researchgate.net\)](#)
- 8) Nabeel, Mohammad Dawod, Investigating Journalists' Lack of Access to Information From Afghan Government Agencies (October 7, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4174387> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4174387>
- 9) Nabeel, Mohammad Dawod, Investigating the Position of Independent Media in Afghanistan from the Interim Administration to the National Unity Government (July 1, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4165130> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4165130>
- 10) Nabeel, Mohammad Dawod, Strengths and Weaknesses of the Ministry of Information and Culture of Afghanistan in Managing Private T.V Stations (From 2010 to 2020) (October 20, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4118303> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4118303>
- 11) Mohmand, Professor Mohammad Rahim, 1392, Administration and Management, Kabul: Dawat Publications.
- 12) Motamed Nejad, Mohammad Kazem. 1386, mass communication tools, Tehran: Allameh Tabatabai University, 6th edition.
- 13) Omid, Hassan. 2009, Omid Farsi Farhang.. Tehran: Rah Rushd Publications, first edition

- 14) Prabakaran, Madhu, What is Good Governance? (February 22, 2011). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1766267> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1766267>
- 15) Saroukhani Baqir, 2014, Sociology of Communication Principles and Basics, Tehran:
- 16) The Unsaid of the Bonn Conference, 17th of August 2016, 8 Sobh newspaper. Interview with Mohammad Natghi.
- 17) <http://afghanistanembassy.org.uk/dari-pashto/%D9%86%D9%82%D8%B4-%D8%AA%DA%A9%D9%86%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%88%DA%98%DB%8C-%D8%AC%D8%AF%DB%8C%D8%AF-%D8%AF%D8%B1-%D8%AA%D8%A7%D9%85%DB%8C%D9%86-%D8%AD%DA%A9%D9%88%D9%85%D8%AA-%D8%AF%D8%A7%D8%B1%DB%8C-%D8%AE/>
- 18) <https://www.dw.com/fa-af/%D9%86%DA%AF%D8%A7%D9%87%DB%8C-%DA%AF%D8%B0%D8%B1%D8%A7-%D8%A8%D9%87-%DA%A9%D8%A7%D8%B1%D9%86%D8%A7%D9%85%D9%87-12-%D8%B3%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%87-%D8%AD%D8%A7%D9%85%D8%AF-%DA%A9%D8%B1%D8%B2%DB%8C/a-17545513>
- 19) [https://fa.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D8%A7%D9%86%D8%AA%D8%AE%D8%A7%D8%A8%D8%A7%D8%AA_%D8%B1%DB%8C%D8%A7%D8%B3%D8%AA%E2%80%8C%D8%AC%D9%85%D9%87%D9%88%D8%B1%DB%8C_%D8%A7%D9%81%D8%BA%D8%A7%D9%86%D8%B3%D8%AA%D8%A7%D9%86_\(%DB%B1%DB%B3%DB%B8%DB%B8\)](https://fa.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D8%A7%D9%86%D8%AA%D8%AE%D8%A7%D8%A8%D8%A7%D8%AA_%D8%B1%DB%8C%D8%A7%D8%B3%D8%AA%E2%80%8C%D8%AC%D9%85%D9%87%D9%88%D8%B1%DB%8C_%D8%A7%D9%81%D8%BA%D8%A7%D9%86%D8%B3%D8%AA%D8%A7%D9%86_(%DB%B1%DB%B3%DB%B8%DB%B8))
- 20) <https://www.irna.ir/subject/83485334/%D8%A7%D9%86%D8%AA%D8%AE%D8%A7%D8%A8%D8%A7%D8%AA-%D8%B1%DB%8C%D8%A7%D8%B3%D8%AA-%D8%AC%D9%85%D9%87%D9%88%D8%B1%DB%8C-%D8%A7%D9%81%D8%BA%D8%A7%D9%86%D8%B3%D8%AA%D8%A7%D9%86-%D8%B3%D9%BE%D8%AA%D8%A7%D9%85%D8%A8%D8%B1-%D9%A2%D9%A0%D9%A1%D9%A9>
- 21) <https://mandegardaily.com/?p=74386>